

ISic1011

I.Sicily inscription 1011

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 160

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. μνήσθητι [ὀθεὸς]
2. τῆς κοιμήσ[εωςκαὶ]
3. ἀναπαύσε[ως]
4. τῆς δούλης [σου]
5. χρηστιανῆ[ςτῆςμο]
6. νάνδρου τῆ[ςκαλο]
7. κμ[ήτου ---]

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492638

EDCS 39102165

PHI 140489

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0191 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.17

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1011. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351396>